

NEWS

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Lately in the Cluster projects...

The Cluster projects were pretty busy. EM-TECH and RHODaS concluded their work so they had some final events and dissemination activities we want to share with you. Also, you can find very interesting news from other projects as well. Read more about it on page 2!

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RTR Conference 2026

The RTR Conference in Brussels was a huge event for the whole Cluster. 11 of the partner projects were able to present their research on stage as part of the 2Zero parallel sessions. On page 3 you can find out how you can access all the presentations and videos.

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Up**

Hi!

Say hello to the latest Cluster member...

The E-VOLVE Cluster community has grown with yet another member. May we proudly introduce: HiVEP - High-voltage power train for efficient electric vehicles. Be sure to get familiar with the project and their research by [following this link!](#)

Lately in the Cluster projects...

Spotlight on

The final weeks of the EM-TECH project were full of dissemination activities to wrap up the research and present the results that were achieved.

At the end of 2025, the project held a very successful webinar about their project outcomes. You can rewatch every webinar session [here!](#)

In addition, the project created one-pagers that give a great overview on all project outcomes they produced in the last three years. Also, there are interviews with the project partners to watch who gave very interesting insights into their work and don't miss out on the latest public deliverables that have been released. Have a look at them [here!](#)

Congratulations from the whole Cluster on successfully wrapping up EM-TECH!

New public deliverables available!

The SmartCorners project published three new public deliverables. Don't miss out on the latest insights into the project.

Here is the list of the published deliverables:

- D3.1: Design report on thermal and cabin comfort control
- D7.2: Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation plan (2)
- D7.3: Communication, Dissemination & Engagement Report

Find the links to the documents via the [SmartCorners Homepage!](#)

DELIVERABLES	
<p>D1.1: Report on SmartCorners technologies and user-centric vehicle control functionalities</p> <p>C. Formento, „Report on SmartCorners technologies and user-centric vehicle control functionalities (D1.1)“, Zenodo, Sep. 2024. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.15607463.</p>	<p>D7.1: Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation plan, detailing the CDE plans, targeted groups & segments, and corporate identity</p> <p>I. Armengaud, V. Ivanov, F. Ratz, S. Kodukulaund M. Ismail, „SmartCorners Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation plan“, Zenodo, Sep. 2024. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.15607552.</p>

Lately in the Cluster projects...

Spotlight on RHODAS

The RHODaS project ended with the year 2025. Here are two more reports from their research:

- [Validating High-Voltage Switching Performance for Next-Generation Electric Powertrains](#)
- [Advancing High-Power Electronics for Heavy-Duty Electric Transport: The RHODaS Hybrid T-Type Converter](#)

RHODaS held a joint webinar in four interconnected sessions exploring the latest European research on next-generation electric powertrain technologies. You can find everything about the event and all the recording [via this link](#).

On the RHODaS website you can also find links to all [public deliverables](#) of the project.

The results of the project were also presented at the final conference in Barcelona. You find a video from the event [here](#) and the itinerary and all details [here](#).

The whole cluster wanted to congratulate for successfully completing the RHODaS project! We appreciate the collaboration!

HighScope released four new public deliverables!

Be sure to check them all out [here](#):

- D2.4 - Simulation results report
- D6.2 - Report on simulation studies for controller tuning and validation
- D3.3 - Report on family of WBG-based integrated traction inverters with dynamically reconfigurable windings and innovative cooling solutions
- D3.4 - Modelling tools to evaluate innovative cooling solutions

RTR Conference 2026

The whole team at the E-VOLVE Cluster booth.

The RTR was a huge event for the E-VOLVE Cluster. We were pleased not only with the opportunity to show the research and results, but especially with the exchange that happened afterwards.

Eleven of the cluster members were present at the conference presenting their projects. First up: Martin Weinzerl for EM-TECH, Fernando Garramiola for HEFT and Dr. Jenni Pippuri-Mäkeläinen for VOLTCAR.

The moderators and presenters from left to right: Gordon Witham, Joao Miranda, Fernando Garramiola, Dr. Jenni Pippuri-Mäkeläinen and Martin Weinzerl

Next were the presentations from Àlber Filbà Martínez for SCAPE, Prof. Wilmar Martínez for PowerDrive, Piotr Bielaczyc for RHODaS, Medina Ćustić for HiPE and Dr. Eric Armengaud for HighScape.

The moderators and presenters from left to right: Tobias Lange, Prof. Wilmar Martínez, Àlber Filbà Martínez, Piotr Bielaczyc, Medina Ćustić, Joao Miranda and Dr. Eric Armengaud

The last E-VOLVE cluster presentations were held by Walter Lukesch for SmartCorners, Thomas Bäuml for MINDED and Alexander Kospach for EFFEREST.

We summed up the event on the cluster homepage. Be sure to find all the presentations, links to the stream of the presentations and some impressions as you [follow this link](#).

Past Events

Driving innovation to real-world performance

The EFFEREST project focuses on using data to design energy-efficient electric vehicles that combine efficiency with user comfort. It improves systems that manage cabin comfort and other vehicle functions, optimizing them in an integrated way to meet users' needs.

A key part of the project is the Real-World Demonstration, in which innovations are tested in modified series vehicles under real driving conditions, supported by virtual simulations. This shows how efficient user-centric solutions perform in practice and validates energy savings and improved user experience.

Twin-Powered EV Drives: MAXIMA leads E-VOLVE Cluster workshop on digital twins

On February 19th, MAXIMA hosted the online interactive workshop “Twin-Powered EV Drives: From Design to Deployment” with fellow E-VOLVE Cluster projects [HEFT](#), [VOLT CAR](#), [ClimaFlux](#) and [HiPE](#).

The workshop started with a series of five-minute pitches from each project, highlighting in which lifecycle phases their digital twins are applied (design, validation and testing, in-vehicle operation, recycling and circularity) and the underlying technological approach.

Overall, EFFEREST bridges the gap between research and real-life solutions, advancing sustainable mobility through affordable and user-centric innovations.

Curious to learn more? Watch EFFEREST's first project video now: [Driving innovation to real-world performance](#)

In addition, the workshop served as basis for a paper that has been accepted for presentation at the SIA Conference. To follow up check out the event details in our [“Upcoming events”](#) section!

Get more infos about the workshop [here!](#)

Autonomous Vehicles, Policy and Research: Key Takeaways from the EARPA Spring Meeting 2026

On 3. and 4. March 2026, the European Automotive Research Partners Association (EARPA) held its Spring Meeting 2026 in Brussels, bringing together nearly 200 participants from across the European automotive research and innovation community.

The two-day event gathered EARPA members, industry experts and policymakers to exchange insights on the future of automotive research and collaboration in Europe.

Initiatives such as the E-VOLVE Cluster

exemplify this approach in practice. By connecting complementary R&D projects across Europe, the cluster is delivering synergies that accelerate the development of the next generation of electric vehicles.

Check out this link to access the event pictures: [Spring Meeting 2026 | Flickr](#) and [read more about it here!](#)

Battery Heroes Workshop on Impact & Sustainability 2025

The Battery heroes cluster is a cluster of battery development related projects that has been created in January 2023 by four battery “sister projects” funded under the same Horizon Europe call, in order to consolidate their collaboration.

Last December the cluster organised a workshop on Impact & Sustainability getting together six different clusters for knowledge exchange.

Find here the [highlight video](#) from the workshop and get some insights from the interactive sessions, panel discussion and cluster booths.

Upcoming Meetings and Conferences

Upcoming Events

TRA
TRANSPORT RESEARCH ARENA

18.5.-21.5.2026
Budapest, Hungary

EPOSS.
European Association on
Smart Systems Integration

16.6.-19.6.2026
EPOSS Annual Forum 2026

SIA SOCIÉTÉ DES
INGÉNIEURS DE
L'AUTOMOBILE

MAXIMA

17.6.-18.6.2026
SIA Powertrain Conference ,
Lille, France
(MAXIMA Digital Twin)

The E-VOLVE Cluster Evolution

From the Achilles project, starting the E-VOLVE Cluster together with the founding projects in 2018, we are expressing our thanks to all project partners and projects contributing with their expertise to the European R&D landscape and collaborating in the E-VOLVE cluster.

